

Spectrophotometric Study of Iron(III) Chelates of *N*-Acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine

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N-Acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine has been recently reported as a spectrophotometric reagent for iron¹. It furnishes purple, orange, and yellow water-soluble complexes with Fe(III) at pH below 1.2, between 1.8 and 3.5, and above 4.0 with absorbance peaks at 490, 470, and 425 m μ respectively. This variation in the nature of the curves is indicative of formation of iron chelates of different compositions at different H⁺-ion concentrations². In the present investigation, the formulas of iron chelates at different pH values have been established spectrophotometrically.

FIG. 1

Standard ferric chloride, the reagent, buffer solutions, and instruments were the same as described earlier¹.

1. Gupta and Sogani, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 769.

2. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.

Iron Chelates.—The molar compositions of iron complexes were investigated by using Job's method⁵ of continued variations. A series of solutions was prepared from $1.3 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions of the metal and the reagent in which the ratios of iron to reagent varied from 23:1 to 1:23. The iron contents in the final solutions were varied between $1.2 M \times 10^{-3}$ and $4.8 M \times 10^{-4}$ at pH 1.0, $6.4 M \times 10^{-4}$ and $1.6 M \times 10^{-4}$ at pH 2.6, and $2.8 M \times 10^{-4}$ and $1.2 M \times 10^{-4}$ at pH 7.0. Absorbances were measured at 490, 470, and 425 m μ respectively. Fig. 1 shows the formation of iron complexes with the reagent. At pH 1.0, the ratio of iron to reagent is 1:1; at pH 2.6, it is 1:1 and 1:2; at pH 7.0, it is 1:3. Thus the formula of the purple-coloured complex is $[FeR_3]^{2+}$; orange complex is a mixture of $[FeR]^{2+}$ and $[FeR_2]^{2+}$, and the yellow complex is FeR_3 .

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⁵ Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **2**, **9**, 113